

ExPaNDS

EOSC Photon and Neutron Data Services

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Introduction to the Taxonomy approach.

In order to increase the findability of publications and datasets, as well as increasing the reporting capabilities of the National RIs, we propose to develop a common taxonomy for the records. Ideally publications databases and data repositories will use the taxonomy developed as part of ExPaNDS to classify and categorise all appropriate records and datasets.

This document, is an example of the direction the taxonomy project could take and is structured in 2 sub-taxonomies:

- Scientific Discipline Taxonomy
- Technical Discipline Taxonomy

This document does not yet include neutron taxonomy and is not intended to be final version of the ExPaNDS taxonomy, but its purpose is to start the development process of the taxonomy. The comprehensive development is going to be a long process as part of the grant project that will require input from many members inside and outside the collaboration.

Scientific Discipline Taxonomy

TOP LEVEL CATEGORY	PARENT CATEGORY (inc. – TAG)
Chemistry	Biochemistry Catalysis Chemical Engineering Inorganic Chemistry Molecular Complexes Molecular Physics Organic Chemistry Physical Chemistry Technique Development - Chemistry Theoretical Chemistry
Earth Sciences & Environment <i>Example keywords:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon Capture • Volcanoes 	Atmospheric Processes Climate Change Corrosion Ecosystems & Biodiversity Evolution Geology Geophysics Marine science/Oceanography Mineralogy - Zeolites Natural disaster, Desertification & Pollution Nuclear Waste Palaeontology Plant science Technique Development - Earth Sciences & Environment Water sciences/Hydrology
Energy <i>Example keywords:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Batteries • Hydrogen Storage • Photovoltaics 	Bioenergy Energy Storage Sustainable Energy Systems Technique Development - Energy
Engineering & Technology	Aerospace Automotive Biotechnology Chemical Engineering Detectors Industrial Engineering Materials Engineering & Processes Technique Development - Engineering & Technology

TOP LEVEL CATEGORY	PARENT CATEGORY (inc. – TAG)
	Transport
Humanities	Cultural Heritage
Information & Communication Technologies	Artificial Intelligence Communication & Networks Components & Micro-systems Computing & software technologies Data management / presentation Data processing Technique Development - ICT
Life Sciences & Biotech <i>Example keywords:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alzheimer's Disease • Brain • Breast Cancer • Ebola • Foot-and-Mouth Disease • Heart • Hepatitis • HIV/AIDS • Influenza • Leukaemia • Lung Cancer • Malaria • Parkinson's Disease • Polio • Tuberculosis 	Agriculture & Fisheries Biochemistry Biophysics Biotech & Biological Systems Evolutionary science Genetics Health & Wellbeing - Antibiotic Resistance - Autoimmune Diseases - Cancer - Carcinogens - Dentistry - Disease in the Developing World - Drug Delivery - Drug Discovery - Infectious Diseases - Neurodegenerative Diseases - Neurology - Non-Communicable Diseases - Ophthalmology - Osteoporosis - Pathogens - Vaccines Structural biology Technique Development - Life Sciences & Biotech
Material Sciences	Biomaterials Ceramics Composite Materials Energy Materials Metallurgy - Metal-Organic Frameworks - Perovskites Polymer Science Quantum Materials - Ferroelectrics - Multiferroics

TOP LEVEL CATEGORY	PARENT CATEGORY (inc. – TAG)
	- Superconductors - Thermoelectrics Radioactive Materials Technique Development - Material Sciences
Physics <i>Example keywords:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giant Magnetoresistance • Graphene • Light-Emitting Diodes (LEDs) • Skymions • Spintronics 	Astronomy/Astrophysics/Astroparticles Dynamics Electronics Hard condensed matter - electronic properties Hard condensed matter - structures High energy & particle physics Magnetism Matter under extreme conditions, warm dense matter, plasmas Metrology Molecular Physics Nanoscience/Nanotechnology Optics Soft condensed matter physics Surfaces, interfaces and thin films Technique Development - Physics

Technical Discipline Taxonomy

TOP LEVEL CATEGORY	PARENT CATEGORY (inc. – TAG)
Diffraction <i>Example keywords:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electron-density studies • Gas-exchange in porous materials • Time-resolved studies of photo-excited states • Single-crystal diffraction studies under an applied electric field 	Anomalous Diffraction Electron Crystallography Energy Dispersive Diffraction (EDD) Grazing Incidence X-ray Diffraction (GIXD) High Pressure Single Crystal Diffraction Low Energy Electron Diffraction (LEED) Macromolecular Crystallography (MX) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fragment Screening - In Situ Diffraction - Long Wavelength Crystallography - Micro/nanofocus MX - Molecular Replacement Multi Wavelength Anomalous Diffraction (MAD) Photo Crystallography Photoelectron Diffraction (PhD) Serial Femtosecond Crystallography (SFX) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time Resolved Serial Femtosecond Crystallography (TR-SFX) Serial Synchrotron Crystallography (SSX) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fixed Target Serial Synchrotron Crystallography (FT-SSX) - Lipidic Cubic Phase Serial Synchrotron Crystallography (LCP-SSX) - Time Resolved Serial Synchrotron Crystallography (TR-SSX) Single Crystal X-ray Diffraction (SXR)D) Single Wavelength Anomalous Diffraction (SAD) Small Molecule Diffraction Surface X-ray Diffraction X-ray Powder Diffraction X-ray Reflectivity (XRR) X-ray Standing Wave (XSW)
Imaging	Coherent Diffraction Imaging (CDI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bragg CDI - Ptychography Infrared Nanospectroscopy Imaging Phase Contrast Imaging Tomography <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cryo Electron Tomography (Cryo ET) - Magnetic X-ray Tomography (MXT) UV Circular Dichroism Imaging X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)
Microscopy	Electron Microscopy (EM) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correlative Light Electron Microscopy (CLEM)

TOP LEVEL CATEGORY	PARENT CATEGORY (inc. – TAG)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cryo Electron Microscopy (Cryo EM) - Cryo Focused Ion Beam Scanning Electron Microscopy (FIBSEM) - PhotoEmission Electron Microscopy (PEEM) - Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) - Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) Infrared Microscopy X-ray Microscopy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correlative Light X-ray Microscopy (CLXM) - Cryo X-ray Microscopy - Scanning X-ray Microscopy - Topography -
Scattering	Anomalous Scattering Pair Distribution Function (PDF) Resonant Inelastic X-ray Scattering (RIXS) Resonant Soft X-ray Scattering (RSXS) Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anomalous Small Angle X-ray Scattering (ASAXS) - Grazing Incidence Small Angle Scattering (GISAXS) - Ultra Small Angle X-ray Scattering (USAXS) Total Scattering Wide Angle X-ray Scattering (WAXS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grazing Incidence Wide Angle Scattering (GIWAXS)
Spectroscopy	Angle Resolved Photoemission Spectroscopy (ARPES) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High Resolution ARPES (HR-ARPES) - Nano ARPES Circular Dichroism (CD) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UV Synchrotron Radiation Circular Dichroism (SRCD) - X-ray Magnetic Circular Dichroism (XMCD) Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) Infrared Spectroscopy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Atomic Force Microscope Infrared Spectroscopy (AFM-IR) - Lab-based Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) - Synchrotron-based Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (SR-FTIR) - Nano Infrared Spectroscopy Linear Dichroism (LD) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - X-ray Magnetic Linear Dichroism (XMLD) Microfocus Spectroscopy Raman Spectroscopy X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy Dispersive EXAFS (EDE) - Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS)

TOP LEVEL CATEGORY	PARENT CATEGORY (inc. – TAG)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- High Energy Resolution Fluorescence Detected XAS (HERFD-XAS)- Microfocus XAS- Near Edge X-ray Absorption Fine Structures (NEXAFS)- X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES) X-ray Emission Spectroscopy (XES) X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (HAXPES) X-ray Photon Correlation Spectroscopy (XPCS)